

SOP Water column collection, filtration, and sample storage for microbiological analyses of microplastics – v5

1. Introduction and Scope

The main purpose of these water and sediment collections is to sample for microplastics (MPs) to analyse microbial communities attached to MPs and to compare them with free-living microorganisms of selected locations of the Red River Delta, Viet Nam.

Two different surveying methods, net and pump, will be used to survey for MPs (> 300 µm) by sampling between 100 L – 400L of three different depths of the water column (surface, mid-water, bottom) across the transect of selected locations (Rn) of the Red River Delta and Cat Ba Island. Locations and depths of collection were selected based on potential sources and sinks of MPs along these locations.

The concentrate of water and debris (including MPs) from both sampling methods (net and pump) will be collected at the cod end of the equipment, said concentrate (approx. 50 mL) is the MPs sample to which this SOP refers to thereafter. For planktonic bacteria, water will be sampled from each listed location and depth (vol. depending on Vietnamese team bottles available), using a Niskin bottle. Nylon filters (NF, pore size 45 µm) will be used to collect debris over 45 µm in size, while membrane filters (MCE, pore size 0.22 µm) will be used to retain free-living bacteria from the water samples.

2. Principle of the Method

Sequential filtration will be used to separate and collect MPs and free-living microorganisms from water samples. 100 L –400L of water will be sampled from each listed location and depth, each resulting in a concentrate of approx. 50 mL. Nylon filters (NF, pore size 45 µm) will be used to collect MPs over 45 µm in size. Collected MPs will be subject of two major different analysis: a) DNA extraction and b) Imaging (Scanning Electron Microscopy, SEM and Fluorescence In Situ Hybridisation FISH), and as such subsamples need to be processed and stored differentially, in an appropriate way for subsequent analysis. Thus, the concentrate will be first split into two fractions (a and b), both of which will be filtered onto NFs. In general, 1 concentrate -> a), b) -> Nylon filters (a, b) => 2 filters per location/depth.

For planktonic bacteria, nylon filters (NF, pore size 45 µm) will be used to collect debris over 45 µm in size, while membrane filters (MCE, pore size 0.22 µm) will be used to retain free-living bacteria from the water samples collected using Niskin bottles.

3. Chemicals and Reagents

- 70% EtOH (alcohol) for sterilisation of equipment.
- 0.2 M Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS)
- 2.5% (w/v) glutaraldehyde (GA)
- PBS [0.2M] / EtOH [100% v/v] 50:50 v/v
- EtOH 50% v/v, 70% v/v, 80% v/v, 90% v/v, 100% v/v

4. Materials and Equipment

- Niskin bottles
- Buckets with lids (x 6)
- Cellulose nitrate membrane filters (0.22 µm pore size, φ 47 mm)
- Nylon filters (45 µm pore size, φ 47 mm)
- Flat tip tweezers

- Gloves
- Falcon tubes (50 mL) for concentrate storage
- Falcon tubes (15 mL) for filter storage
- Cooler with dry ice on board / fridge
- Freezer on facilities near sampling sites
- Vacuum filtration equipment (glass funnels, HDPE tubing, and pump)
- Portable scale (min. 0.0 g accuracy) for sediment subsampling
- Stainless steel spatula / spoon

5. Method for water collection and filtration

5.1 Water collection for microplastics recovery

- 5.1.1 Water (100 L – 400 L) from each location (RR1, RR3, CB) and depth are sampled for MPs by the method selected (net or pump method) at the following locations: Refer to the [MicrobiologyUK-MolecularBiologyFieldSamples_Nov22](#) for an updated version of samples names and locations.
- 5.1.2 Immediately upon retrieval, the resulting concentrate (water and debris, including MPs), thereafter “samples”, will be transferred onto a 50 mL Falcon tube, and placed in a fridge at 4C until further processing on board of the boat or on land.

5.2 Water filtration for microplastics recovery

- 5.2.1 Following antiseptic techniques (gloves, surfaces sprayed with 70% ethanol (EtOH) and wiped with a lint-free 100% cotton cloth, water samples will be split into two fractions (a, b of 25 mL each) for subsequent DNA extraction and SEM analysis.
- 5.2.2 Before sample filtration, flat tweezers and vacuum filtration device will be wiped with 70% EtOH. Distilled water will be passed through before every experimental session.
- 5.2.3 Nylon net filters (pore size 45 µm) will be placed onto the filtration device, using flat tweezers, to collect microparticles on the sample.
- 5.2.4 This step will be repeated twice for each sample fraction (a and b). One of the resulting filters, holding MPs, will be placed into an empty Falcon tube and immediately stored at –80 C or into lysis buffer for subsequent MPs retrieval and DNA analysis. The second filter, for MPs imaging analyses (SEM and FISH) will be stored in a Falcon tube containing enough GA (2.5 % v/v) to cover the filter (approx. 4 mL) for 2 h.

Depending on the accessibility to a freeze dryer, imaging filters can be either dehydrated (step 5.2.5) or be transferred from GA, into fresh tubes and stored in 50:50 EtOH 100 % v/v and PBS (0.2 M) and keep at – 20 C.

- 5.2.5 Dehydration step. Imaging filters will be transferred into PBS (0.2 M) and placed in fresh Falcon tubes with EtOH 50 % v/v. After 10 mins, the EtOH will be discarded and replaced with EtOH 70 % v/v. Following 10 mins more, the EtOH solution will be again discarded and replaced with EtOH 80% v/v, and then 90% v/v. After 10 mins more the solution will be replaced with EtOH 100%. The last dehydration step (EtOH 100% v/v) will be repeated twice. At the end of the EtOH gradient the tubes must be placed in the freezer (- 80 C) or further processed for SEM and FISH analysis (refer to SOP Scanning Electron Microscopy of environmental microplastics, SOP Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation of environmental microplastics).

- 5.2.6 On every instance, filters will be removed using EtOH wiped tweezers. Filters will be moved (by the opposite edges, forming U shape) into a plastic storage tube. Note: Wet filters will be a bit more pliable, and efforts will be taken to not to crease the filter. The back of the wet filters can stick to the inside of the tube, if filter chips/breaks, all the pieces will be placed inside a separate tube.
- 5.2.7 Tubes will be labelled with location and depth of water filtered using a permanent waterproof tape. Separate tubes will be used for each filter.

5.3 Water filtration for planktonic microorganisms recovery

- 5.3.1 Water (vol. depending on available Niskin bottles) from each location and depth will be sampled to concentrate planktonic microorganisms by deploying Niskin bottles at the following locations:
Refer to the [MicrobiologyUK-MolecularBiologyFieldSamples_Nov22](#) for an updated version of samples names and locations.
- 5.3.2 Immediately upon retrieval, the content of the Niskin bottle will be poured into a clean, ethanol-wiped bucket of an appropriate volume, and closed with a lid until filtration. The Niskin bottle will be deployed again to obtain triplicates.
- 5.3.3 Water filtration will be performed on the boat, although it is expected that due to the large volume of water, the process will be slow and the samples will have to wait to be processed.

5.4 Water filtration for planktonic microorganisms recovery

- 5.4.1 Before sample filtration, flat tweezers and vacuum filtration device will be wiped with 70% EtOH. Distilled water will be passed through before every experimental session.
- 5.4.2 Nylon net filters (pore size 45 µm) will be placed onto the filtration device, using flat tweezers, to remove debris from the sample, and the resulting filter will be discarded.
- 5.4.3 For each individual sample, water collected in the receiving flask from the vacuum filtration system will be transferred into a clean container after every filtration step required to filter the total collected volume (vol. depending on Niskin bottle).
- 5.4.4 The total resulting filtrated water (vol. depending on Niskin bottle) will then be filtered through a cellulose membrane filter (0.22 µm) to collect the free-living microorganisms. Water collected in the receiving flask will be discarded as often as required until the full sample volume has been filtered.
- 5.4.5 Filters will be stored in tubes and kept cold (4 C) until stored at – 80C or inside tubes with lysis buffer to be frozen at - 20C.
- 5.4.6 Tubes will be labelled with location and depth of water filtered using a permanent waterproof tape. Separate tubes will be used for each filter.

6 Microplastics contamination control and monitoring

Due to the ubiquity of microplastic fibres in the environment, preventive measures must be taken to reduce and monitor potential sources of contamination. The equipment will be wiped with 70% EtOH using a lint-free 100% cotton cloth and allowed to dry fully. Equipment and samples will be covered wherever possible to minimize environmental exposure. Additionally, procedural blanks will be run in parallel with samples to monitor environmental contamination. For this, a glass Petri dish with a damped glass filter will be left open next to the working area during the various stages of sample environmental exposure, while falcon tubes with the different reagents but without samples will be processed as described above. The resulting control filters will be examined under a stereo microscope to correct for potential air-borne and/or procedural plastic contamination.

7 Documentation

Clear labelling of the tubes will be required. The labels need to include location, depth, and date of

collection.

8 Safety

[Risk Assessment.](#)

9 References

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[Fang et al., 2015 Front. Environ. Sci. Eng. 9\(3\): 444–452 DOI 10.1007/s11783-014-0679-4](#)
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